

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

GA no 101000607

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st June 2021. End date: 31st May 2025

Public Executive Summary of Deliverable D1.8
Feasibility studies and market replication strategy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607

Disclaimer: This publication reflects only the author's view, and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Executive summary log

Submission	05-05-2025
Lead beneficiary-organisation	NORCE
Responsible person	C. Rørvik
Name and affiliation contributing persons	L. Tobin (REDINN), S. Hollmann (SBSM), A. Bassegoda (LEITAT), R. M. Ree (NORCE), O. Romero (UAB), Y. Fredes Tapia (UAB), M. Montalban (UAB), G. Bjerga (NORCE)
Name and affiliation internal reviewers	G. Bjerga (NORCE), K. Schnorr (NOVO)

Main achievements/outcomes**Summary**

The Deliverable D1.8 presents a feasibility study for each of the four innovation cases worked on in OXIPRO (WP5, Task 5.1-5.4) and the purpose is to map business opportunities. The market replication strategy presents the possibility of transferring or 'copying' results from one case to another. This included an exploration of novel enzyme applications in key sectors (Task 5.5).

Textile case

Key technical task: Utilization of carbohydrate oxidases for circular bio-bleaching processes.

The OXIPRO project seeks to revolutionize cotton bleaching through a one-bath, enzyme-based process that reduces water, energy, and chemical use, promoting circular bio-bleaching and wastewater reuse. Traditional methods are resource-intensive, but OXIPRO's enzymatic approach is more sustainable while preserving fabric quality. Using stable enzymes, the process lowers electricity by 10%, heat by 15%, and chemicals by 20%, with minimal infrastructure changes. Though it requires initial investment, the project offers long-term environmental and market advantages. Legal hurdles are minimal, and operational upgrades are manageable. OXIPRO is on track, with enzyme development underway and ongoing efforts to enhance enzyme stability.

Sunscreen case

Key technical task: Biocatalytic synthesis of melanin-like polymers for sunscreen ingredients.

OXIPRO has developed an enzymatic technology for the synthesis of melanin like polymers. Within the project, this technology has been validated obtaining a polymer with good SPF, but limited application due to its colour and low hydrophobicity. This technology is versatile and enables the synthesis of other polymers that could meet the requirements for sunscreen manufacture in future.

Detergent case

Key technical task: Development of novel oxidoreductases compatible with liquid laundry detergents. OXIPRO has developed a new oxidoreductase and demonstrated it can achieve bacterial eradication in in vitro assays in combination with a liquid detergent formula employing operational conditions. These results open the door to develop a detergent with an oxidoreductase with sanitizing claims. Future developments need to be addressed to launch this detergent formulation onto the market.

Nutraceutical case

Key technical task: Application of enzymes in fish processing to optimize the sensory attributes. OXIPRO has developed methods to produce the required amounts of enzyme by fermentation and the fish protein hydrolysates by enzymatic hydrolysis required for experimental testing and validation. Due to very high costs on cofactor supplements, the feasibility of the innovation, is limited, - unless cofactor management strategies are developed. Significant progress was made on cofactor recycling within OXIPRO, although this alone will not be sufficient to enable market uptake of the enzyme technology.